

A Blockchain Based Approach for Demand Response Management in Internet of Vehicles

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Abstract— Electric Vehicles (EVs), as well as the number of applications for their management, are rapidly increasing due to the fact that Internet of Vehicles (IoV) becomes more informative and industrialized. According to the literature, IoV requires decentralization towards the energy Demand Response (DR) management, with secure energy trading, efficient charging scheduling, and incentives for making the drivers to participate. Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) can be used to enable a foundational environment to support DR management. However, and to the best of our knowledge, none of the existing research works discussed in the literature adopts a holistic approach to address them. As such there is a demand for exploring a unified blockchain-based framework for distributed DR management. Therefore, the aim of this work is focused on the blockchain adoption in IoV-assisted smart cities. More specifically, we propose a blockchain based approach, to be used for building a secure and user-centric DR management framework. Our proposition aims to address the DRP in IoV through charging scheduling based on the generation of EV driving profiles, and optimal Vehicle-to-Vehicle/Grid (V2V | V2G) energy trading.

Keywords—blockchain, internet of vehicles, demand response, charging scheduling, driving profiling, V2V, V2G, smart city

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

More than half of the world's population lives in cities, with that number expected to rise to approximately 70% by 2050 [1]. The rising demand for energy is a result of the movement to metropolitan regions. It is therefore expected that cities will account for 75% of global energy use by 2030 [2]. To cover the increased demand for energy, new methods for its production and management are currently undertaken, moving to the so-called smart cities. Energy management within smart cities encompasses a variety of parties, most of which are highly decentralized, such as energy users and service providers, who utilize energy during their day-to-day activities. Smart mobility has already been recognized as a crucial component for the development of smart cities, encouraging sustainability, guarantying connectivity, and improving transportation networks, as mentioned in [3].

Smart cities often rely on a smart grid infrastructure to enable the bi-directional communication between the energy users and service providers. In order to manage and control the smart grid, smart homes, Electric Vehicles (EVs), smart meters and a variety of renewable energy sources (e.g. sensors) and devices are coordinating and linked with each other.. As a consequence of those advancements, traditional systems and control devices are being overtaken by more sophisticated systems known as Cyber Physical Systems (CPSs). The CPSs are based on the integration of computation, networking, and physical processes in order to provide a bridge between the digital and physical environments [4]. Recently, CPSs attracted a growing interest and are now widely used in many areas of everyday life. Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) is a common type of CPS. The primary goal of ITS is to build a transportation system that is convenient, safe, dynamic, and efficient [5].

Within the ITS, a concept named Internet of Vehicles (IoV) is introduced (Fig. 1), which is powered by smart vehicles, IoT, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) [6]. Smart vehicles can communicate with each other, as well as, with drivers, passengers, and Road Side Units (RSUs) through the internet and Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) technologies [7]. In addition to smart cars, the IoV ecosystem includes vehicular communication systems, RSUs, and cloud platforms. A vehicular communication system is often referred to as a Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X). V2X enable the interaction between vehicles and other entities (i.e., vehicle, infrastructure, grid, pedestrian etc.), and vice versa, as defined in [8]. The most important communication examples are Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G).

Despite the widespread use of EVs, several challenges concerning smart energy management (e.g., energy imbalances) need to be further explored and resolved. In terms of balancing the load and supply, a large number of centralized generators and energy storage devices must be installed, resulting in considerable capital and operational expenses [9].

A possible solution is DR management, which can be used in IoV-assisted smart cities to enable energy prosumers (i.e., EV drivers; that act both as consumers and as producers) to proactively change their energy usage habits based on an incentivized model (with embedded rewards under certain conditions or policies) [10][18]. The combination of DR and IoV, offers a potential method to balance out peak demand and minimize instability without adding extra generators and storage devices [11]. Furthermore, the cost of EVs causes a significant load on V2G energy trading for demand response management, as highlighted in [11][12]. As a result, a dependable solution is required to meet the future energy needs of industrial and residential customers while also supporting the charging and discharging requirements of EVs [13].

A decentralized blockchain approach could potentially address much of the challenges associated with smart mobility and IoV DR challenges. Although blockchains are highly coupled with the used of cryptocurrencies (e.g., Bitcoin), its properties can be adopted for use in the energy sector including sustainability, IoT, smart cities, smart mobility and more [14]. At its heart, blockchain comprises of a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) and a distributed data structure (i.e., the ledger) that is cryptographically secured and made irreversible through a consensus process i.e., reaching consent between a set of potentially and unknown untrusted peers. A blockchain protocol can provide an infrastructure for enabling various types of secure EV transactions over a network of vehicles e.g., trading of energy; to be performed in a decentralized, transparent and secure manner. In addition, it could enable a trusted layer for the implementation of decentralized applications for energy, such as the development of an energy exchange, a layer for safeguarding digital identities, a shared economy, and for recording data that could then be used to derive EV charging patterns [15]. Since blockchain technology has the potential to significantly increase energy efficiency, decrease management costs and guarantee the effective use of the energy resources, its application in IoV concept providing secure, autonomous and automated energy trading between EVs, is becoming essential.

Fig. 1. IoV as part of the smart city

For example, Brooklyn microgrid is one of the first applied engineering programs of energy blockchain [16]. The whole project is based on P2P energy trading using blockchain while it does not require a traditional and/or third-party energy supplier. In an attempt to overcome the smart grid imbalances and to control the ever-growing energy demands from EVs, the authors of [17] proposed a P2P energy trading scheme between EVs and the service providers. Furthermore, the authors of [18] propose a blockchain-enabled DR scheme with an individualized incentive pricing model, while authors in [19] present a framework for user-centered access to electric charging facilities via blockchain based energy trading.

Considering the above discussion, the IoV that utilizes a blockchain layer has the potential to create a new ecosystem for the transportation and automobile sectors, in which energy may be exchanged and preserved in a secure, transparent, immutable, and efficient manner. Furthermore, incorporating blockchain technology into the existing IoV might result in significant benefits in terms of safety, efficiency and demand response management.

B. Contributions

Regarding the Demand Response Management (DRM) in smart cities, V2V and V2G technology plays a key role in balancing energy demand and supply among EVs and charging stations. However, security and privacy, data processing and transparency are all issues that must be addressed. Therefore, there is a gap related to the investigation of a blockchain based DRM framework that holistically tackles most of the identified problems. To the best of our knowledge, none of the related studies [20] have succeeded to tackle all of the identified issues holistically. Therefore, this kind of investigation, and the proposition of a unified blockchain framework for IoV DRM, would contribute to both the academia and the industry since it would provide the basis for real-life use case evaluations. This paper proposes a Proof-of-Authority (PoA) based blockchain approach for enabling the secure trading of energy in a P2P manner as a solution to the demand response management in the IoV. Moreover, we propose the profiling of EVs and the driving habits/preferences of their drivers to

propose optimized charging/discharging schedules across a smart city. Our approach aims to minimize energy imbalances with a city and manage DR needs. Finally, we propose the deployment of an incentivization model to encourage end-users to participate in V2V/V2G energy trading.

C. Outline

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the concept overview, focusing on the mobility within IoV and the attempt to manage demand and response through blockchain, as well as the identified involved entities. Section III provides details in regard to the blockchain adoption in the IoV demand response, while Section IV introduces a high-level description of our proposition with the proposed workflow. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. OVERVIEW & INVOLVED ENTITIES

A. Concept Overview

The proposed approach intends to promote IoV mobility through prosumer-centric and EV-centric services, allowing the usage of information exchange in the mobility context while also facilitating V2V/V2G energy trading to address the DR problem. Our approach suggests the optimization of charging scheduling by monitoring the driver's behavior. At the same time, the proposed approach aims to improve the customer driving experience towards the energy demand response management. As a result, through V2V/V2G energy trading, a continuous cycle of energy demand monitoring will be established, and efficient response establishment will be settled. Integration of vehicle data with other data sources (traffic information, geographic data, meteorological data, etc.) from RSUs, as well as real-time analysis of energy demand, are also of particular interest.

As described in Section III, CSs and RSUs are installed at various sites in a smart city. To reach any CS for charging or discharging their batteries, EVs should travel a certain distance. Furthermore, there is a great deal of ambiguity about future driving incidents in realistic scenarios. EVs seek to know the needed parameters for this, such as the required distance and charging time to reach a charging point. Furthermore, knowing the ideal charging schedules based on driver's data, which are referred to as EV

Fig. 2. Concept overview

profiles and are unique to each driver, provides us with a significant benefit. As a result, our approach intends to first develop a safe and reliable local network based on blockchain, where EVs may charge and collaborate efficiently. Secondly, we aim to generate EV driving profiles for all prosumers engaged, based on daily consumption habits, driving style, driving routes, and other factors, so that we can better understand the energy demand within the IoV. Thirdly, optimal charging schedules will be established based on the corresponding profiles in order to deliver personalized charging/discharging schedules to prosumers, hence addressing part of the demand-response problem in a smart city. Finally, we suggest an incentivization scheme that will provide rewards and/or penalties in order to encourage EV drivers to engage in such a scheme and minimize their apprehension. A typical scenario of our approach is depicted in Fig. 2.

C. Involved Entities

The following entities (depicted in Fig. 3) are identified and their anticipated role within the proposed DRM Framework is presented.

1) *Prosumer*: A prosumer can be considered as an end-user that not only consumes energy, but also produces energy [21]. In the sense of ENTSO-E [22], a prosumer is connected to the IoV combining the roles of a consumer and a producer. Prosumers are the parties who operate EVs and are involved in charging/discharging procedures in order to ensure the balance of the grid.

2) *Electric Vehicle*: This paper considers EVs as Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), which typically include controllable loads, distributed generation and energy storage. In the scope of this work, the role of EVs, is to use the aggregated demand response from EVs' charging in order to ensure demand and response balance. Enabling V2V and V2G technology, EV will facilitate energy trading to provide their surplus energy back to the grid to fulfil energy demand.

3) *Bidirectional Charging Station (CS)*: Bidirectional charging provides not only for charging of EV batteries, but also for the extraction of energy from car batteries and its transmission back to the grid [23]. Bidirectional charging stations will enable the V2G idea, which will allow electricity to be supplied from an EV car's battery to the grid, which is often built in the EV charger. Within the scope of this paper the bidirectional charging stations refer to the entities that enable the V2G and help to balance the local energy demands via smart and efficient charging/discharging.

4) *Registration Authority*: A Registration Authority (RA) is a credential enrolment operation used in public key infrastructures. The Registration Authority (RA) is in charge of registering all entities involved (i.e., prosumers, EV, CSs, aggregators). In order to authenticate nodes in the blockchain network, the RA produces public (PK) and private key (SK) pairs. To become trusted network entities, all entities involved in the framework should register with the RA.

5) *Road-Side Units (RSU)*: An RSU is a roadside wireless communication device (i.e., operating as Dedicated Short-Range Communication) that offers connectivity and information assistance to moving vehicles, such as safety alerts and traffic information [24]. An example of RSU is a smart traffic light. For this paper we consider RSUs responsible for providing traffic information. Thus, it will become known in which parts of the grid (i.e., smart city) there is increased energy demand due to traffic.

Fig. 3. Involved entities

6) *Local Aggregators (LA)*: A local aggregator is a form of energy service provider that may increase or decrease the energy usage of a group of users based on overall grid demand [25]. The aggregator's role is to maximize the value of the available energy by delivering it to the entity with the greatest need. In the scope of this paper, a LA can enter into an arrangement with numerous prosumers under which.

III. BLOCKCHAIN FOR DEMAND RESPONSE

In the proposed blockchain DRM framework, a blockchain network would be utilized to keep an immutable record of energy transactions and for the registration of all entities involved. The end-users of the proposed framework will then be able to trust their transactions being accurately recorded by a system and cannot be tampered.

To protect the integrity of the blockchain network, all involved entities request to the RA for a public key (PU) and a private key (PK). The blockchain network creates a system that describes the interaction between EVs and CSs, such as the quantity of energy that EVs require from the CS and the incentives to be provided. As described in section IV, during P2P energy trading, EVs transmit energy demand requests to the blockchain network, which are subsequently approved or declined by the respective CSs based on charging schedules and produced profiles. All transactions between the participating entities are

encrypted, signed and organized into blocks. These blocks are broadcasted to the blockchain network for verification and validation, which may be accomplished using the PoA consensus algorithm. PoA is considered an appropriate choice for a CA for our proposed framework due to its speed and scalability properties, as explained in [26]–[28]. Furthermore, unlike proof-of-work (PoW) and proof-of-stake (PoS), it does not need much computational power and thus no high energy demand, making it a more environmentally friendly algorithm. Fig 4 depicts an example of the interconnections between the blockchain involved entities.

IV. WORKFLOW OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

In this section the workflow of the proposed approach is presented and illustrated in Fig. 5.

1) Registration to the DRM Framework and trust establishment

By registering to the framework, participants (e.g., a prosumer with an EV) authenticate with the system while their data is recorded on the blockchain. The related data, such as the ID, public key, hash of essential data, and other information, are included in blocks, expanding the chain. As already mentioned, during the registration, each entity is provided with a private and public key pair, and a node address. The key pairs are used for identity management between the entities whenever P2P communication is taking place. After the registration to the network the entity authenticates using the blockchain's registration information. After authentication, the integrity of entity is checked using the hash of the provided information in order to detect probable intrusion (i.e., malicious) activity. In case the entity is successfully

Fig. 4. Blockchain for secure P2P trading for DRM

registered and authenticated, it can participate to the DRM through secure P2P communication with the rest of the registered (i.e., authenticated) entities.

2) Generation of EV profiles

This process aims to extract EV load patterns for various user groups that are likely to affect the energy demand within the IoV. The corresponding process is triggered during the first trip of an EV, under the condition that the starting place of the first trip is “home”. During the generation of the EV profiles the system also records driving behavior, charging needs, trip distance etc., to be used for later. EV driving behavior and prosumer mobility is also considered aiming at energy demand management. In addition, daily EV profiles for different types of preferences and different energy consumption patterns will be generated, that will be later used for the formulation of EV charging schedules.

3) Formulation of charging schedules

Next, personalized charging/discharging schedules for the prosumers will be formulated, based on their generated EV profiles. The goal is to optimize the charging/discharging process. The relevant flow is triggered after the completion of the first trip of an EV. Assuming that the prosumer’s profile is already generated, the charging schedule is generated. The generation of charging/discharging schedules will consider the drivers profile and personal needs, the IoV demand and response.

Specifically, traffic information (obtained by RSUs) will be taken under consideration as well as peak and off-peak hours. Charging/discharging schedules will be formulated for each prosumer. The schedules generated will be used for tackling the energy imbalances within the IoV network.

4) Estimation of energy demand

During the estimation of the energy demand, the LA requests the estimated energy for a selected area and timeframe. Then, the aggregated energy from all relevant entities (i.e., EV, CSs) will be calculated and provided to the Aggregator. This information will be used by the Aggregator in a later stage for handling the P2P transactions. The aggregated energy is available and can be used if needed in IoV transactions or for DRM.

Fig. 5. Proposed Blockchain DRM Framework Workflow

5) V2G/V2V Energy Trading

During the V2V/V2G energy trading, the EV will provide their surplus energy back to the grid to fulfil the energy demand and settle possible energy imbalances. The relevant flow is triggered when an EV or the Aggregator broadcast the need the energy demand to utilize V2G or V2V energy trading (i.e., charging or discharging energy). Three different scenarios can be triggered within this flow: (a) an EV user makes a request to purchase energy (i.e., demands energy), (b) an EV user makes a request to sell energy (i.e., energy response) and (c) the LA broadcasts specific demand/response needs to the IoV area.

The interested entity broadcasts through the aggregator a demand request (either manually or automatically based on the defined charging schedules). Upon receiving the request, the LA will broadcast the request to the most suitable entities (e.g., either a neighboring CS or another passing EV), based on specified parameters such as distance, available energy etc. The interested entity selects with which entity wish to establish a secure connection, and the P2P transaction takes place. The charging/discharging transaction is completed and the DRM is settled.

6) Provisioning of rewards and penalties

Finally, incentives should be provided. The motivation behind the incentives provisioning is (a) to encourage prosumers to participate in the DRM Framework and (b) to discourage malicious activities in the network. The provisioning of rewards or penalties is triggered when an entity broadcasts a demand for energy within the IoV. Incentives are given to prosumers based on their creditability. Specifically, upon the successful completion of a P2P energy transaction the reputation of a prosumer is increased and is rewarded (e.g., with tokens). In case a broadcast message is discovered to be malicious by the RA, or the integrity of the prosumer (or EV) is compromised, the creditability is reduced and not awarded.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Nowadays, blockchain has obtained great research interest in many industries, including the IoV. Blockchain technology is proposed and utilized, while it has been realized that it could tackle several challenges such as the centralization and to improve the architecture of the IoV by building a decentralized and secure vehicular environment. In the context of smart mobility, blockchain can be used for transactions relating to charging, V2G energy trading or serving as a foundation for communication between vehicles. Although initial approaches about this topic exist, the identified challenges are partially resolved. Therefore, in this paper we proposed a unified blockchain framework for DRM in IoV. This work proposes a blockchain DRM framework at the abstract level focusing on describing the involved entities as well as a describing the proposed workflows.

The next step for our work is to complete the design and implementation of the presented approach, while we aim to enhance the interactions between the involved entities. Furthermore, we envision the need for a deeper investigation in terms of interoperability of the EVs over the blockchain network. Lastly, we note that future research should be conducted in relation to real-time adoption of charging scheduling based on IoV monitoring and the EVs' quality of experience.

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